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Tyrosine hydroxylase neurons regulate growth hormone secretion via short-loop negative feedback

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1 **Tyrosine hydroxylase neurons regulate growth hormone secretion via short-loop negative**
2 **feedback**

3

4 **Abbreviated title:** TH cells control GH release via negative feedback

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40 **Abstract**

41 Classical studies suggest that growth hormone (GH) secretion is controlled by negative-
42 feedback loops mediated by GH-releasing hormone (GHRH)- or somatostatin-expressing neurons.
43 Catecholamines are known to alter GH secretion and neurons expressing tyrosine hydroxylase
44 (TH) are located in several brain areas containing GH responsive cells. However, whether TH-
45 expressing neurons are required to regulate GH secretion via negative-feedback mechanisms is
46 unknown. In the present study, we showed that between 50 to 90% of TH-expressing neurons in
47 the periventricular, paraventricular and arcuate hypothalamic nuclei and locus coeruleus of mice
48 exhibited STAT5 phosphorylation (pSTAT5) after an acute GH injection. Ablation of GH receptor
49 (GHR) from TH cells or in the entire brain markedly increased GH pulse secretion and body growth
50 in both male and female mice. In contrast, GHR ablation in cells that express the dopamine
51 transporter (DAT) or dopamine beta-hydroxylase (DBH; marker of noradrenergic/adrenergic cells)
52 did not affect body growth. Nevertheless, less than 50% of TH-expressing neurons in the
53 hypothalamus were found to express DAT. Ablation of GHR in TH cells increased the hypothalamic
54 expression of *Ghrh* mRNA, although very few GHRH neurons were found to co-express TH and
55 GH-induced pSTAT5. In summary, TH neurons that do not express DAT or DBH are required for
56 the autoregulation of GH secretion via a negative-feedback loop. Our findings revealed a critical
57 and previously unidentified group of catecholaminergic interneurons that are apt to sense changes
58 in GH levels and regulate the somatotropic axis in mice.

59

60 **Keywords:** catecholamines; dopamine; hypothalamus; neuroendocrinology; neuropeptides;
61 somatotropic axis.

62 Significance Statement

63 Textbooks indicate until now that the pulsatile pattern of GH secretion is primarily controlled
64 by GHRH and somatostatin neurons. The regulation of GH secretion relies on the ability of these
65 cells to sense changes in circulating GH levels in order to adjust pituitary GH secretion within a
66 narrow physiological range. However, our study identifies a specific population of tyrosine
67 hydroxylase-expressing neurons that is critical to auto-regulate GH secretion via a negative-
68 feedback loop. The lack of this mechanism in transgenic mice results in aberrant GH secretion and
69 body growth. Since GH plays a key role in cell proliferation, body growth and metabolism, our
70 findings provide a major advance to understand how the brain regulates the somatotropic axis.

71 **Introduction**

72 Growth hormone (GH) is produced by somatotrophic cells of the anterior pituitary gland
73 under the control of different factors secreted by the hypothalamus into the hypophyseal portal
74 system (Steyn et al., 2016). Although numerous neuropeptides, neuromodulators, hormones and
75 metabolites regulate GH secretion, hypothalamic neurons that express GH-releasing hormone
76 (GHRH) or somatostatin (SST) play a key role controlling the pulsatile pattern of GH secretion in
77 humans and rodents (Steyn et al., 2016). Whereas neuroendocrine SST neurons located in the
78 hypothalamic periventricular (PV) and paraventricular (PVH) nuclei exert an inhibitory effect on GH
79 secretion, hypophysiotropic GHRH neurons in the ventrolateral arcuate nucleus (ARH) stimulate
80 GH release (Fodor et al., 2006).

81 The pulsatile pattern of GH secretion is auto-regulated by negative-feedback loops that act
82 in hypothalamic neurons (Nass et al., 2000a) or pituitary gland (Nass et al., 2000b). Besides these
83 GH-mediated negative-feedback mechanisms, changes in circulating levels of ghrelin (Nass et al.,
84 2008; Xie et al., 2015) or insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) (Morita et al., 1987; Gahete et al.,
85 2011) also modulate pituitary GH secretion. SST neurons, rather than GHRH cells, likely represent
86 the major GH negative-feedback node in the brain (Wagner et al., 1998). While 70% of SST
87 neurons of the PV and PVH express the GH receptor (GHR) (Burton et al., 1992), less than 10% of
88 GHRH neurons contain *Ghr* mRNA (Burton et al., 1995). Central administration of *Ghr* mRNA
89 antisense decreases *Sst* mRNA in the PV leading to increased GH pulsatility, without affecting
90 *Ghrh* expression (Pellegrini et al., 1996). However, GHRH neurons are drastically affected by
91 changes in GH levels (Chomczynski et al., 1988; Bertherat et al., 1993; de Gennaro Colonna et al.,
92 1993), indicating that indirect neural circuits detect changes in circulating GH and regulate GHRH
93 secretion accordingly. Neurons that express SST or neuropeptide Y (NPY) are potential candidates
94 for this indirect regulation since these cells express GHR (Burton et al., 1992; Chan et al., 1996;
95 Kamegai et al., 1996) and exert a regulatory effect on GHRH neurons (Catzeflis et al., 1993;
96 Minami et al., 1998). However, ablation of GHR in ARH neurons that co-express the agouti-related
97 protein (AgRP) and NPY causes no changes in GH secretion or body growth (Furigo et al., 2019).

98 Using the capacity of an acute systemic GH injection to induce the phosphorylation of
99 STAT5 (pSTAT5), we mapped the distribution of GH responsive cells in the mouse brain (Furigo et

100 al., 2017). We confirmed the presence of GH responsive neurons in the PV, PVH and ARH, and
101 further demonstrated that GH can robustly induce pSTAT5 in other brain structures, including the
102 locus coeruleus (LC). LC is the major site responsible for the release of noradrenaline in the
103 forebrain and LC lesions lead to increased GH secretion (Bluet-Pajot et al., 1992). Additionally,
104 GHRH and SST neurons receive noradrenergic inputs from brainstem neurons (Iqbal et al., 2005).
105 Importantly, α 2-adrenergic agonists, such as clonidine, stimulate GH secretion, while agonists of
106 α 1- and β -adrenergic receptors inhibit GH release (Steyn et al., 2016). Dopaminergic neurons are
107 also located in hypothalamic areas containing GH responsive cells. Of note, disruption of the D2
108 dopamine receptor in the central nervous system reduces GH secretion and hypothalamic *Ghrh*
109 expression causing dwarfism (Diaz-Torga et al., 2002; Noain et al., 2013). Thus, catecholaminergic
110 neurons, including noradrenergic and dopaminergic cells, seem to be implicated in the
111 hypothalamic control of GH secretion. However, it is still unknown whether catecholaminergic
112 neurons are responsive to GH and if ablation of GHR in these cells affects the pulsatile GH
113 secretion and consequently body growth. Therefore, the objective of the present study was to
114 investigate whether different groups of catecholaminergic neurons are required to regulate GH
115 secretion via negative-feedback mechanisms. For this purpose, we first identified
116 catecholaminergic neurons that are responsive to GH. Then, we used different mouse models to
117 study the consequences of the genetic ablation of GHR in catecholaminergic, dopaminergic or
118 noradrenergic/adrenergic cells, and in the entire brain.

119

120 **Materials & Methods**

121 *Mice*

122 Adult (12 week-old) C57BL/6 wild-type male mice were used to identify catecholaminergic
123 neurons that are responsive to GH. To induce the ablation of GHR in specific subpopulations of
124 catecholaminergic neurons, mice carrying loxP-flanked *Ghr* alleles (Fan et al., 2009; List et al.,
125 2013) were bred with the dopamine transporter (DAT)-IRES-Cre mouse (Stock No: 006660, JAX®
126 mice), dopamine beta-hydroxylase (DBH)-Cre mouse (Parlato et al., 2007) or tyrosine hydroxylase
127 (TH)-Cre mouse (Stock No: 008601, JAX® mice). Inactivation of GHR in the entire brain was
128 achieved by breeding mice carrying loxP-flanked *Ghr* alleles with the Nestin-Cre mouse (Stock No:

129 003771; JAX® mice). The resulting heterozygous mice for the *Ghr*^{flox} mutation and positive for Cre
130 allele were further crossed with *Ghr*^{flox/flox} mice, generating *Ghr*^{flox/flox} mice carrying the Cre gene
131 (DAT GHR KO, DBH GHR KO, TH GHR KO or BRAIN GHR KO mice). Control groups were
132 composed of *Ghr*^{flox/flox} littermates that were negative for the Cre gene. To visualize DAT and SST
133 neurons, DAT-IRES-Cre and SST-IRES-Cre (Stock No: 018973, JAX® mice) mice were crossed
134 with the LoxP-Stop-LoxP tdTomato-reporter mouse (Stock No: 007909, The Jackson Laboratory).
135 GHRH neurons were visualized using young adult *Ghrh*^{Cre/-}/eGFP-L10a mice (Rupp et al., 2018),
136 kindly provided by Dr. Martin Myers (University of Michigan, now available at JAX® mice, Stock
137 No. 031096). The mutations were confirmed by genotyping the DNA previously extracted from the
138 tail tip of all mice using a commercially available kit (REDEExtract-N-Amp™ Tissue PCR Kit,
139 Sigma). Mice were produced and maintained in standard conditions of light (12-h light/dark cycle)
140 receiving a regular rodent chow diet. All experiments were carried out in compliance with National
141 Institutes of Health guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals and were previously
142 approved by the Ethics Committee on the Use of Animals of the Institute of Biomedical Sciences at
143 the University of São Paulo (protocol No: 73/2017).

144

145 *Detection of GH responsive neurons*

146 To visualize GH responsive neurons, adult male mice received an acute i.p. injection of
147 porcine pituitary GH [20 µg/g, from Dr. A.F. Parlow, National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive
148 and Kidney Diseases–National Hormone and Pituitary Program (NIDDK-NHPP)]. *Ghrh*^{Cre/-}/eGFP-
149 L10a mice received an acute i.p. injection of mouse recombinant GH (20 µg/g; NIDDK-NHPP).
150 PBS-injected mice were used as controls. Ninety minutes after the injections, mice were deeply
151 anesthetized with isoflurane and perfused transcardially with saline, followed by a 10% buffered
152 formalin solution. Brains were collected and post-fixed in the same fixative for 60 min and
153 cryoprotected overnight at 4 °C in 0.1 M PBS containing 20% sucrose. Brains were cut in 30-µm
154 thick sections using a freezing microtome. Brain slices were rinsed in 0.02 M potassium PBS, pH
155 7.4 (KPBS), followed by pretreatment in water solution containing 1% hydrogen peroxide and 1%
156 sodium hydroxide for 20 min. After rinsing in KPBS, sections were incubated in 0.3% glycine and
157 0.03% lauryl sulfate for 10 min each. Next, slices were blocked in 3% normal donkey serum for 1 h,

158 followed by incubation in anti-pSTAT5^{Tyr694} primary antibody (Cell Signaling, Cat# 9351, 1:1000;
159 RRID: AB_2315225) for 40 h. After incubation in the primary antibody, slices were submitted to
160 fluorescence reaction or immunoperoxidase staining according to the experiment. For the
161 immunofluorescence reactions, sections were rinsed in KPBS and incubated for 90 min in
162 AlexaFluor⁴⁸⁸-conjugated secondary antibody (1:500, Jackson ImmunoResearch). For the
163 immunoperoxidase staining, sections were incubated for 1 h in biotin-conjugated secondary
164 antibody (1:1,000, Jackson ImmunoResearch) and next for 1 h with an avidin-biotin complex
165 (1:500, Vector Labs). The peroxidase reaction was performed using 0.05% 3,3'-diaminobenzidine
166 and 0.01% hydrogen peroxide. TH-immunoreactivity (TH-ir) was detected in brain sections
167 incubated overnight in anti-TH primary antibody (GmbH, Cat# MO22941-100, 1:1,000; RRID:
168 AB_1624244), followed by incubation for 90 min in AlexaFluor⁵⁹⁴- or AlexaFluor⁴⁰⁵-conjugated
169 secondary antibodies (1:500 and 1:250, respectively; Jackson ImmunoResearch). To co-localize
170 GHRH and TH cells in the ARH, brain sections of *Ghrh^{Cre/-}/eGFP-L10a* mice were incubated
171 overnight at 4 °C in either sheep anti-TH (Millipore, Cat# AB1542, 1:2,000; RRID: AB_90755) and
172 chicken anti-GFP (Aves Labs, Cat# GFP-1020, 1:10,000; RRID: AB_10000240) primary
173 antibodies. Subsequently, sections were rinsed and incubated in AlexaFluor594-conjugated anti-
174 sheep IgG and AlexaFluor488-conjugated anti-chicken IgG antibodies (1:500, Invitrogen) for 1.5
175 hour. All sections were mounted onto gelatin-coated slides and the slides were covered with
176 Fluoromount G mounting medium (Electron Microscopic Sciences, Hatfield, PA).
177 Photomicrographs were acquired with an Axio Imager A1 (Carl Zeiss, Munich, Germany) or Axio
178 Imager M2 (Carl Zeiss) microscopes. The number and percentage of single-, double- or triple-
179 labeled cells in the areas of interest were determined in one or two rostrocaudal levels of the PV
180 (Bregma: -0.34 mm), PVH (Bregma: -0.70 and -0.82 mm), ARH (Bregma: -1.34 and -1.58 mm),
181 substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc; Bregma: -2.92 mm) and LC (Bregma: -5.40 mm).

182

183 *Dual label in situ hybridization and immunohistochemistry*

184 The *Ghrh* DNA template was generated from mouse hypothalamic RNA by PCR
185 amplification of a 402 bp region, starting at position 105 nt (NM_010285). The antisense radio-
186 labeled riboprobe was generated by *in vitro* transcription using T7 RNA polymerase (Promega).

187 Dual-label *in situ* hybridization (ISH) and immunohistochemistry was performed to confirm the
188 distribution of *Ghrh* transcript in GHRH-eGFP+ neurons. Free-floating sections from adult GHRH-
189 eGFP female mice ($n = 3$) were treated with 0.1% sodium borohydride for 15 min and with 0.25 %
190 acetic anhydride in DEPC-treated 0.1 M triethanolamine (TEA, pH 8.0) for 10 min. Sections were
191 incubated overnight at 50°C in the hybridization solution containing the ³⁵S-labeled *Ghrh* riboprobe.
192 Subsequently, sections were treated with RNase A for 30 minutes and submitted to stringency
193 washes. Sections were blocked in 3% BSA, then incubated with a primary chicken anti-GFP
194 antibody (1:10000) overnight at 4°C. Sections were incubated for 1 h in donkey biotinylated anti-
195 chicken IgG (1:1000, Jackson ImmunoResearch), followed by 1 h incubation with avidin-biotin
196 complex (1:500, Vector Labs). The detection reaction was performed using 0.05% 3,3'-
197 diaminobenzidine and 0.01% hydrogen peroxide. Sections were mounted onto SuperFrost plus
198 slides, dipped in NTB-2 autoradiographic emulsion and stored in light-protected boxes at 4°C for 3
199 weeks. Slides were developed and mounted with DPX medium.

200

201 *Evaluation of somatic growth*

202 To determine possible changes in somatic growth, different groups of male and female
203 mice at approximately 10, 20 or 42 weeks of age were weighed and their body fat and lean masses
204 were measured by time-domain nuclear magnetic resonance using the LF50 body composition
205 mice analyzer (Bruker, Germany). Naso-anal length and the masses of the liver, spleen, heart,
206 kidney, perigonadal adipose tissue, testicle, brain and gastrocnemius muscle were also
207 determined. Serum IGF-1 concentration was determined by ELISA (#MG100; R&D Systems).

208

209 *Evaluation of pulsatile GH secretion*

210 To minimize stress interference during the blood collection, disposable cardboard tubes
211 were placed inside the cages and each mouse was handled daily in these cardboard tubes. This
212 procedure was performed for 30 days before the experiment to acclimate to the procedure of tail-
213 tip blood sampling. Experiments started at the beginning of the light cycle (7:00 h) and 36
214 sequential tail-tip blood samples of 5 µl were collected from each mouse at 10 min intervals (Steyn

215 et al., 2011). Each animal was sampled on a single day, over a six-hour period. Immediately before
216 the first sample collection, a small portion of the tail tip (1 mm) was cut with a surgical blade to
217 allow the collection of small drops of blood. During the whole period of the experiment, mice were
218 allowed to move freely in their home cage with *ad libitum* access to food and water. For each blood
219 collection, mice were placed inside the cardboard tube and quickly held by the base of the tail.
220 Using a 10 μ l pipette, a 5 μ l sample of whole blood was collected and transferred to 105 μ l of PBS
221 with 0.05% tween-20 (PBS-T). After each blood collection, a fingertip pressure was gently applied
222 to the tail tip to stop bleeding. This procedure practically causes no stress to the animals, otherwise
223 stress-induced tail vasoconstriction due to sympathetic activation would prevent any detection of
224 hormonal pulsatile secretion. Samples were immediately placed on dry ice and stored at -80 °C for
225 later analysis. We completed the assessment of pulsatile GH secretion in both 8 and 18 week-old
226 male mice.

227 For the assessment of GH levels in the whole blood, we used a GH sensitive sandwich
228 ELISA adapted from a protocol published by Steyn et al (2011). A 96-well high-binding plate (9018,
229 Corning, Kennebunk, ME) was coated with 50 μ L of monkey anti-rat GH antibody (rGH-IC-1,
230 AFP411S, NIDDK-NHPP; RRID: AB_2665564) diluted in PBS at 1:50,000 overnight at 4 °C. After
231 decanting the coating antibody, wells were incubated with 200 μ L of blocking buffer (5% skim milk
232 powder in PBS-T) for 2 h at room temperature. The standard curve consisted of a 2-fold serial
233 dilution of mouse recombinant GH (mGH reference preparation, AFP-10783B, NIDDK-NHPP) in
234 0.2% bovine serum albumin (BSA) PBS-T. The wells were incubated with 50 μ L of samples at a
235 1:20 dilution for 24 h at room temperature. The plate was washed in PBS-T and the wells were
236 incubated with 50 μ L of rabbit anti-rat GH antibody (AFP5672099, NIDDK-NHPP; RRID:
237 AB_2721132) diluted in blocking buffer at 1:100,000 for 24 h at 4 °C. After washing in PBS-T, wells
238 were incubated with 50 μ L of horseradish peroxidase conjugated goat anti-rabbit IgG antibody
239 (A9169-2ml, Sigma-Aldrich) diluted in 50% PBS, 50% blocking buffer at 1:30,000 for 90 minutes at
240 room temperature. After a final wash in PBS-T, wells were incubated with 100 μ L of 2 mg/mL o-
241 phenylenediamine dihydrochloride (OPD, P1526, Sigma-Aldrich) in citrate-phosphate buffer (pH
242 5.0) containing 0.02% hydrogen peroxide for 45 minutes at room temperature. The reaction was
243 stopped with 50 μ L of 3 M HCl. The absorbance was determined at 490 nm with a microplate

244 reader (Epoch, Biotek) and the wavelength of 650 nm was used for background correction. The
245 standard curve ranged from 0.03 to 15 ng/mL and the concentration of GH was calculated by
246 interpolating the optical density of the samples against a nonlinear regression of the standard
247 curve. The lower limit of detection was 0.04 ng/mL, and the intra-assay and inter-assay coefficients
248 of variation were 2.6% and 9.7%, respectively. GH pulses were detected using the DynPeak pulse
249 detection algorithm (Vidal et al., 2012). Default parameters of the algorithm were used, with the
250 exception of the global relative threshold increased from 20% to 50% to reduce probability of
251 detecting false positive pulses. The number of GH pulses was calculated for the period of 6 h. The
252 amplitude of each pulse was defined as the difference between peak value and its nadir, and the
253 average levels of the detected pulses were considered for the statistical analysis of pulse
254 amplitude. Mean GH was calculated by averaging all GH values from each mouse.

255

256 *Quantitative real-time PCR*

257 Total RNA from the whole hypothalamus was extracted with TRIzol (Invitrogen).
258 Assessment of RNA quantity and quality was performed with an Epoch Microplate
259 Spectrophotometer (Biotek). Total RNA was incubated in DNase I RNase-free (Roche Applied
260 Science). Reverse transcription was performed with 2 µg of total RNA with SuperScript II Reverse
261 Transcriptase (Invitrogen) and random primers p(dN)6 (Roche Applied Science). Real-time
262 polymerase chain reaction was performed using the 7500™ Real-Time PCR System (Applied
263 Biosystems) and Power SYBR Green or TaqMan PCR Master Mixes (Applied Biosystems).
264 Relative quantification of mRNA was calculated by $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$. Data were normalized to the geometric
265 average of *Actb*, *Gapdh* and *Ppia* and reported as fold changes compared to values obtained from
266 the control group (set at 1.0). The following primers were used: *Actb* (forward: gctccggcatgtgcaaag;
267 reverse: catcacaccctggtgccta), *Gapdh* (forward: ggggccagcttaggtcat; reverse:
268 tacggccaaatccgttcaca), *Ghr* (forward: atcaatccaagcctggggac; reverse: acagctgaatagatcctgggg),
269 *Ghrh* (forward: tatgcccggaaagtgtaccag; reverse: atccttgggaatccctgcaaga), *Ppia* (forward:
270 tatctgactgccaagactgagt; reverse: ctcttgctggtcttgccattcc), *Sst* (forward: ctgtctgcccgtctccagt;
271 reverse: ctgcagaaactgacggagtct) and *Th* (TaqMan assay; Mm00447557_m1; ThermoFisher
272 Scientific).

273

274 *Statistical analysis*

275 Data were analyzed by the unpaired two-tailed Student's *t* test (two groups) or one-way
276 ANOVA (three groups), followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. Statistical analyses
277 were performed using the GraphPad Prism software. We considered *P* values < 0.05 to be
278 statistically significant. All results are expressed as mean \pm s.e.m.

279

280 **Results**281 *Distribution of catecholaminergic neurons that are responsive to GH in the mouse brain*

282 GH responsive neurons are abundantly found in numerous brain regions that contain
283 catecholaminergic neurons, including the PV, PVH and ARH in the hypothalamus and the LC in the
284 pons (Furigo et al., 2017). To determine whether catecholaminergic neurons are directly
285 responsive to GH, C57BL/6 male mice received an acute GH injection and analysis of co-
286 localization between GH-induced pSTAT5 and TH-ir was performed in brain sections. We
287 observed that $61 \pm 8\%$ of TH immunoreactive neurons in the PV (Fig. 1A), $69 \pm 8\%$ in the PVH
288 (Fig. 1B), $53 \pm 5\%$ in the ARH (Fig. 1C) and $86 \pm 3\%$ in the LC (Fig. 1D) expressed pSTAT5 after
289 GH injection. Some co-localizations were found in other subpopulations of catecholaminergic
290 neurons, including those located in the dorsomedial nucleus of the hypothalamus, ventral
291 tegmental area, C1 and A1 groups in the ventrolateral medulla and in the nucleus of the solitary
292 tract. PBS-injected mice showed a very small number of pSTAT5 positive cells in the brain and
293 virtually no co-localization with TH neurons (Fig. 1E-F). Thus, several subpopulations of
294 catecholaminergic neurons are responsive to GH.

295

296 *Cell-specific ablation of GHR in different types of catecholaminergic neurons*

297 The evidence of functional GHR in catecholaminergic neurons suggest that these cells are
298 apt to sense circulating GH levels and consequently regulate pituitary GH secretion via negative-
299 feedback loops. To investigate the role of GH action on catecholaminergic neurons to regulate GH
300 secretion and consequently somatic growth, we generated mice carrying cell-specific ablations of
301 GHR in different types of catecholaminergic neurons. Since TH is a shared marker of all

302 catecholaminergic cells, we used TH-Cre mice to induce deletion of GHR in all dopaminergic and
303 noradrenergic/adrenergic cells (TH GHR KO mice). To target specifically dopaminergic cells, DAT-
304 IRES-Cre mice were used to ablate GHR in cells that express the dopamine transporter (DAT GHR
305 KO mice). GHR deletion only in noradrenergic and adrenergic cells was achieved using the DBH-
306 Cre mouse (DBH GHR KO mice). Finally, Nestin-Cre mouse was used to induce GHR ablation in
307 the entire brain (BRAIN GHR KO mice). To confirm the cell-specific deletion in these mouse
308 models, we co-localized GH-induced pSTAT5 with markers of each subpopulation of
309 catecholaminergic neurons (Fig. 2). GH injection in DAT GHR KO mice induced pSTAT5 in a large
310 number of cells in the hypothalamus (Fig. 2A) and brainstem, as expected. However, using
311 tdTomato reporter protein as a marker of DAT cells, we observed that virtually no DAT cell in the
312 hypothalamus co-localized with GH-induced pSTAT5 in DAT GHR KO mice (Fig. 2A). As shown in
313 wild-type mice, 95 ± 2% of TH positive noradrenergic neurons in the LC exhibited pSTAT5 after
314 GH injection in DAT GHR KO mice, demonstrating that the target deletion only affected
315 dopaminergic cells. In DBH GHR KO mice, a large number of pSTAT5 cells were observed in the
316 hypothalamus (inset in the Fig. 2B), whereas noradrenergic neurons of the LC no longer expressed
317 GH-induced pSTAT5 (Fig. 2B). GH injection in TH GHR KO mice was unable to induce pSTAT5 in
318 TH immunoreactive cells of the hypothalamus (Fig. 2C) and LC (Fig. 2D), whereas a normal
319 distribution of pSTAT5 was observed in brain areas that do not contain TH neurons, such as the
320 ventromedial nucleus of the hypothalamus or ventromedial part of the ARH (Fig. 2C). As
321 demonstrated in previous publications (Furigo et al., 2019; Teixeira et al., 2019), brain-specific
322 GHR ablation caused a robust reduction in GH-induced pSTAT5 expression in the entire
323 hypothalamus and brainstem (Fig. 2E-F). Additionally, BRAIN GHR KO mice exhibited a 90%
324 reduction in the expression of *Ghr* mRNA in the whole hypothalamus, compared to control animals,
325 as determined by quantitative real-time PCR (Control: 1.00 ± 0.09; BRAIN GHR KO: 0.11 ± 0.01;
326 $t_{(8)} = 8.501$, $P < 0.0001$). Altogether, these findings demonstrate the specificity and efficacy of our
327 cell-specific gene deletions.

328

329 *GHR ablation in TH cells or the entire brain causes increased body growth in male and female*
330 *mice*

331 To investigate the consequences of GHR ablation in different subpopulations of
332 catecholaminergic neurons, we evaluated the body weight, body composition, naso-anal length
333 and the masses of different organs and tissues in DAT GHR KO, DBH GHR KO, TH GHR KO and
334 BRAIN GHR KO mice. Each conditional knockout group has its own control group consisting of
335 animals born in the same litters. In 20 week-old males, we observed that both DAT GHR KO and
336 DBH GHR KO mice exhibited a similar body weight, lean mass, fat mass and naso-anal length,
337 compared to their respective control groups (Fig. 3A-H). Accordingly, the masses of the liver,
338 spleen, heart, kidney, perigonadal adipose tissue, testicle, brain and gastrocnemius muscle were
339 similar between control groups and DAT GHR KO and DBH GHR KO mice (Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). In
340 contrast, both 10 week-old (Fig. 3I-L) and 42 week-old (Fig. 3M-P) TH GHR KO mice had
341 increased body weight, lean mass and naso-anal length compared to control groups. In addition,
342 42-week-old TH GHR KO male mice exhibited a higher liver, spleen, heart, kidney (Fig. 4), testicle,
343 brain and gastrocnemius masses (Fig. 5), compared to control animals. Interestingly, body fat
344 mass (Fig. 3K and Fig. 3O) and perigonadal adipose tissue weight (Fig. 5I) were similar between
345 TH GHR KO and control mice, demonstrating that the increased body weight was not caused by a
346 higher body adiposity. Ablation of GHR in the entire brain causes loss of GH negative feedback
347 (Bohlen et al., 2019; Furigo et al., 2019). Thus, BRAIN GHR KO mice were studied as a reference
348 to the effects caused by GHR ablation in catecholaminergic cells. We observed that BRAIN GHR
349 KO male mice exhibited increased body weight, lean mass and naso-anal length, compared to
350 control group (Fig. 3Q-T). BRAIN GHR KO mice also showed higher liver, spleen, heart, kidney
351 masses (Fig. 4M-P), whereas body fat (Fig. 3S), perigonadal adipose tissue and testicle (Fig. 5M-
352 N) masses had no significant differences between control and BRAIN GHR KO mice.

353 Possible changes in body growth were also evaluated in female mice (Fig. 6). As seen in
354 males, 10-week-old DAT GHR KO and DBH GHR KO female mice showed similar body weight,
355 lean mass and body fat mass, compared to their respective control groups (Fig. 6A-F). In contrast,
356 both TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO female mice exhibited increased body weight and lean
357 mass in comparison with control females (Fig. 6G-H and Fig. 6J-K). No differences were observed
358 in body fat mass between TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO females and control mice (Fig. 6I and
359 Fig. 6L).

360

361 *Loss of GH negative feedback in TH cells or the entire brain raises GH secretion via increased*
362 *pulse amplitude*

363 To test if the absence of GH action in TH cells leads to increases in GH secretion, we
364 initially measured serum IGF-1 levels in 10 week-old TH GHR KO and control male mice. We
365 observed increased serum IGF-1 levels in TH GHR KO mice (861 ± 43 ng/mL) compared to control
366 animals (635 ± 47 ng/mL; $t_{(17)} = 3.532$, $P = 0.0026$). Then, we analyzed the pulsatile secretion of
367 GH in 8- or 18-week-old male mice (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8). Both 8-week-old TH GHR KO and BRAIN
368 GHR KO mice exhibited higher mean GH levels during the period analyzed, compared to control
369 group (Fig. 7A-C and Fig 8A). Therefore, the increased body growth of TH GHR KO and BRAIN
370 GHR KO mice was probably caused by the greatly increased GH secretion. To determine which
371 parameters of pulsatile GH secretion were affected by the loss of GH negative feedback, the
372 frequency and the amplitude of pulses were determined. Eight-week old BRAIN GHR KO mice
373 displayed a reduced number of pulses during the 6-hour blood collection period, compared to
374 control animals (Fig. 8B). On the other hand, a marked increase in pulse amplitude was observed
375 in both 8-week-old TH GHR KO mice, compared to control animals, and BRAIN GHR KO mice,
376 compared to all groups (Fig. 7A-C and Fig. 8C). To investigate whether the changes in GH
377 secretion continue in older animals, the pulsatile secretion of GH was also evaluated in 18 week-
378 old male mice. In this case, TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO mice showed similar mean GH
379 levels, pulse frequency and pulse amplitude, compared to control animals (Fig. 7D-F and Fig. 8D-
380 F). These findings indicate that the loss of GH negative feedback in TH cells increases GH
381 secretion via higher pulse amplitude, without altering pulse frequency. Furthermore, these
382 neuroendocrine defects decrease with aging.

383

384 *Partial co-localization between DAT and TH in the hypothalamus*

385 Our findings so far indicate that GH action on TH positive neurons, but not on DAT- or
386 DBH-expressing cells, are required for typical GH secretion and consequently normal somatic
387 growth. Whereas DBH expression reliably represents the distribution of noradrenergic/adrenergic
388 cells (Parlato et al., 2007), there is evidence that only part of TH cells in the forebrain expresses

389 DAT (Turiault et al., 2007; Yip et al., 2018). In this regard, we performed a co-localization in male
390 mice between DAT-expressing cells (using the tdTomato reporter protein) and TH-ir in several
391 hypothalamic areas and in the SNpc, as a positive reference (Fig. 9). We observed that $56 \pm 3\%$ of
392 TH immunoreactive neurons in the ARH (Fig. 9A), $28 \pm 2\%$ in the PV (Fig. 9B) and $9 \pm 8\%$ in the
393 PVH (Fig. 9C) expressed tdTomato. In contrast, $95 \pm 1\%$ of TH immunoreactive neurons in the
394 SNpc expressed tdTomato (Fig. 9D). Thus, it is likely that only a subpopulation of TH positive cells
395 in the hypothalamus was actually affected by the GHR ablation using the DAT-IRES-Cre mice. To
396 confirm that the GHR deletion only affected the subpopulation of DAT-expressing neurons in the
397 hypothalamus of DAT GHR KO mice, GH-induced pSTAT5 was co-localized with either TH-ir (Fig.
398 9E), or tdTomato, as marker of DAT-expressing neurons only (Fig. 9F). Interestingly, while GH-
399 induced pSTAT5 was clearly observed in hypothalamic TH immunoreactive cells (Fig. 9E), DAT-
400 expressing cells did not contain pSTAT5 (Fig. 9F). Taken together, these results demonstrate that
401 TH neurons that do not express DAT are required for the auto-regulation of GH secretion via a
402 negative-feedback mechanism.

403

404 *GHR ablation in TH cells increases hypothalamic expression of Ghrh, although a very small*
405 *percentage of GHRH cells are responsive to GH and express TH*

406 To determine how GHR ablation in TH cells or the entire brain affects the hypothalamic
407 expression of classical neuropeptides that regulate GH secretion, we collected the hypothalamus
408 of 8 week-old control, TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO male mice. We initially determined the
409 mRNA levels of *Th*, but no significant differences between the groups were observed (Fig. 10A).
410 Then, *Sst* and *Ghrh* mRNA levels were assessed in the whole hypothalamus. *Sst* mRNA levels
411 were also similar between the groups (Fig. 10B). In contrast, TH GHR KO mice showed increased
412 *Ghrh* mRNA expression compared to control animals, and BRAIN GHR KO mice exhibited higher
413 *Ghrh* mRNA levels compared to both control and TH GHR KO mice (Fig. 10C).

414 Using reporter mice that allow the visualization of SST or GHRH cells, we performed a triple
415 immunofluorescence labeling to identify whether these neurons co-express TH and are responsive
416 to GH. Although a large percentage of SST neurons, especially in the periventricular zone of the
417 hypothalamus, expressed pSTAT5 in response to GH, as expected (Burton et al., 1992), no triple-

418 labeled neurons were observed (Fig. 10D-E). GHRH-Cre mouse was used in a previous
419 publication (Rupp et al., 2018), but details about the percentage of GHRH neurons that show Cre
420 recombinase activity in the ARH were not provided. Thus, using brain sections of *Ghrh^{Cre/-}/eGFP-*
421 *L10a* mice, dual-labeled neurons coexpressing eGFP-immunoreactivity and GHRH ³⁵S (silver
422 grains) were quantified in the ARH (Fig. 11A-C). One section and one side of two adult female
423 mice were quantified. Only cells containing silver grains (*Ghrh* mRNA) 3x above background levels
424 overlaying a brown (DAB stained) cytoplasm were considered positive. We found that $52.5 \pm 7.5\%$
425 of GHRH-Cre eGFP neurons coexpress *Ghrh* mRNA in adult mice (Fig. 11A-C). Of note, very few
426 GHRH hybridization signal was observed outside GFP-immunoreactive neurons. Next, we
427 determined whether GHRH-Cre eGFP neurons in the ARH co-express TH and are responsive to
428 GH. GH-induced pSTAT5 was observed in $8.7 \pm 1.9\%$ of GHRH cells (data from two females and
429 one male), compared to $1.3 \pm 0.7\%$ in PBS-injected mice ($t_{(5)} = 4.053$, $P = 0.0098$; data from two
430 females and two males; Fig. 11D-G). As shown in previous studies (Phelps et al., 2003; Bouyer et
431 al., 2007), $13 \pm 1\%$ of GHRH neurons in the ARH co-expressed TH (Fig. 11D-G). However, only
432 $2.5 \pm 1.6\%$ of GHRH neurons co-expressed TH and pSTAT5 after an acute GH injection,
433 compared to $0.9 \pm 0.7\%$ in PBS-injected mice ($t_{(5)} = 0.9904$, $P = 0.3675$; Fig. 11D-G). Therefore,
434 although the absence of GHR in TH cells leads to increased *Ghrh* mRNA expression, only a very
435 small percentage of GHRH cells are responsive to GH and express TH.

436

437 Discussion

438 The secretion of pituitary hormones is primarily regulated by negative-feedback systems. In
439 most of these feedback loops, specific hypothalamic neurons detect changes in hormone levels
440 and modulate pituitary function to maintain hormone concentrations within a narrow range (Steyn
441 et al., 2016). Regarding the somatotrophic axis, the common knowledge indicates that GH feeds
442 back mostly to SST and GHRH neurons (Steyn et al., 2016). Even though SST and GHRH
443 neurons are indispensable for the regulation of the somatotrophic axis (Donahue and Beamer, 1993;
444 Zeyda et al., 2001), interneurons that express GHR may also play a role regulating GH secretion.
445 Both noradrenergic (Lal et al., 1975; Bluet-Pajot et al., 1992; Iqbal et al., 2005) and dopaminergic
446 (Diaz-Torga et al., 2002; Noain et al., 2013) neurotransmission have also been associated with the

447 regulation of GH secretion. However, our study revealed that not only a high percentage of
448 catecholaminergic neurons are directly responsive to GH, but the absence of GHR from TH cells
449 disturbs the hypothalamic control of GH secretion, leading to increases in GH pulse amplitude and
450 body growth. Remarkably, the increased mean GH levels between TH GHR KO mice and BRAIN
451 GHR KO mice was similar, highlighting that the lack of GH action on TH neurons produces defects
452 equivalent to the absence of GHR in the entire brain. Since GHR deletion in TH- and Nestin-
453 expressing cells caused identical alterations in the body growth of males and females, we believe
454 that the increased GH secretion observed in experiments performed only in males occurs in
455 females as well. However, GH secretion presents significant sex differences (van den Berg et al.,
456 1996; Jaffe et al., 1998). Thus, future studies are still necessary to confirm that the higher body
457 growth observed in TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO female mice is also caused by increased GH
458 secretion.

459 The infusion of α 2-adrenergic agonists has been widely used as a clinical test to evaluate
460 possible defects in GH production in children and adolescents (Gil-Ad et al., 1979; Steyn et al.,
461 2016). The discovery that approximately 90% of noradrenergic cells of the LC are directly
462 responsive to GH indicates that the noradrenergic control of GH secretion might integrate a
463 feedback control loop. However, ablation of GHR in DBH-positive cells caused no changes in body
464 growth. Thus, the role of GH action on the LC remains unknown and deserves further investigation.
465 DAT GHR KO mice also exhibited similar body growth compared to control littermates, suggesting
466 that GH signaling in DAT-expressing cells is not required for the regulation of GH secretion. DAT is
467 responsible for the reuptake of dopamine in the synaptic cleft. Although DAT expression has been
468 used as a marker of dopamine neurons, our findings and previous studies (Turiault et al., 2007; Yip
469 et al., 2018) indicate that the majority of TH-positive neurons in the hypothalamus does not
470 express DAT. Hypothalamic dopaminergic neurons are frequently associated with the regulation of
471 anterior pituitary hormone secretion, releasing neuromodulators into the hypophyseal portal system
472 without requiring DAT for the reuptake of dopamine (Brown et al., 2016). Since TH GHR KO mice
473 exhibited increased body growth, whereas both DAT GHR KO and DBH GHR KO mice showed a
474 normal phenotype, our findings indicate that a group of non-DAT dopaminergic neurons (TH
475 positive, but DBH negative) is critical to the auto-regulation of GH secretion via a negative-

476 feedback loop. Prolactin release is mainly controlled by tuberoinfundibular dopamine neurons
477 (Brown et al., 2016). Thus, the regulation of prolactin and GH secretion seems to be somehow
478 coordinated by these hypothalamic dopaminergic neurons. Accordingly, dopamine agonists are
479 clinically used to treat hyperprolactinemia and acromegaly (Jaffe and Barkan, 1994; Diez and
480 Iglesias, 2000). These drugs inhibit GH secretion by acting in pituitary somatotrophic cells (Spada et
481 al., 1994; Ben-Shlomo et al., 2017) or via hypothalamic mechanisms (Vance et al., 1987; West et
482 al., 1997). However, some TH neurons in the hypothalamus possibly produce L-DOPA as an end-
483 product rather than dopamine (Meister et al., 1988; Komori et al., 1991). Although their function is
484 not well understood, there is evidence of cooperative synthesis of dopamine by different neurons
485 that express complementary enzymes of the pathway for dopamine biosynthesis (Ugrumov et al.,
486 2002; Kurina et al., 2017). Thus, the exact neurotransmitters used by these TH+/DAT-/DBH-
487 neurons to regulate GH secretion still need to be identified.

488 Another question investigated was whether these catecholaminergic neurons that regulate
489 the somatotrophic axis would be the same cells that produce SST or GHRH. SST neurons are
490 distributed in the same hypothalamic nuclei that contain GH-responsive TH cells (Fodor et al.,
491 2006). In agreement with previous studies that identified a large percentage of SST neurons
492 expressing GHR in the PV/PVH (Burton et al., 1992), we also observed a large amount of SST
493 neurons in these areas expressing GH-induced pSTAT5. Some co-localizations between SST and
494 pSTAT5 were also observed in the ARH. However, virtually no triple-labeled pSTAT5/SST/TH cells
495 were found in these brain areas. Histological and molecular data indicate that part of GHRH
496 neurons express TH (Bouyer et al., 2007; Campbell et al., 2017). Surprisingly, scarce information
497 exists regarding the expression of GHR in GHRH neurons. As far as we know, one study reported
498 that less than 10% of ARH GHRH neurons express *Ghr* mRNA (Burton et al., 1995). Using
499 pSTAT5 as a marker of GH responsive cells, we confirmed the small number of GHRH-responsive
500 neurons and less than 3% of them express both TH and GH-induced pSTAT5. Therefore, TH cells
501 that regulate GH secretion via negative feedback are basically DAT, DBH, SST and GHRH
502 negative, representing a yet unidentified group of neurons critical to the auto-regulation of the
503 somatotrophic axis.

504 Hypothalamic *Ghrh* mRNA expression was disturbed by GHR deletion in TH cells or the
505 entire brain. Rather than a downregulation of *Ghrh* expression, which would indicate an attempt to
506 correct high circulating GH levels via negative feedback, we observed increased *Ghrh* expression
507 in the hypothalamus of TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO mice. Thus, our findings confirm the
508 results of previous studies indicating that GHRH neurons are influenced by variations in GH levels
509 (Chomczynski et al., 1988; Bertherat et al., 1993; de Gennaro Colonna et al., 1993), and further
510 demonstrate that this auto regulation involves interneurons that first detect changes in GH levels
511 and, in response, regulate GHRH expression. Thus, we hypothesize that the absence of GH action
512 on these TH+/DAT-/DBH- neurons led to either increased excitatory signal or decreased inhibitory
513 tone on GHRH neurons. In both cases, increased GHRH seems to represent the final path for the
514 stimulation of GH secretion caused by the lack of GH negative-feedback effect on these neurons.
515 Notably, *Ghrh* expression was higher in BRAIN GHR KO mice compared to TH GHR KO mice.
516 Thus, *Ghrh* expression is not only regulated by GH action on TH cells, but also by another
517 neuronal population that causes an additive effect. Although less than 10% of GHRH neurons are
518 directly responsive to GH, ablation of GHR in this subgroup of GHRH neurons may account for the
519 upregulation in hypothalamic *Ghrh* expression. Alternatively, another population of GH-responsive
520 interneurons may also affect *Ghrh* expression. However, we cannot rule out the possibility that
521 these TH+/DAT-/DBH- neurons might regulate GH secretion through the hypophyseal portal
522 system.

523 Even though both TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO mice exhibited equivalent increases in
524 mean GH levels, the pulsatile pattern of GH secretion was differently affected in these mouse
525 models. BRAIN GHR KO mice showed reduced GH pulse frequency that was compensated by a
526 robust increase in GH pulse amplitude. The absence of GH negative feedback in TH cells also led
527 to increased pulse amplitude. Intracerebroventricular administration of GHR antagonist increases
528 GH pulse amplitude without affecting the number of GH pulses (Nass et al., 2000a). Despite the
529 fact that the differences in body growth persists in older TH GHR KO and BRAIN GHR KO mice,
530 the pulsatile pattern of GH secretion was normalized in 18 week-old knockout mice. Previous
531 studies have already shown a significant decline in GH secretion throughout adulthood in mice
532 (Huang et al., 2012; Xie et al., 2015). Interestingly, aging-related decline in GH secretion is caused

533 by a decrease in GH pulse amplitude, whereas pulse frequency remains unchanged (Russell-Aulet
534 et al., 2001). Therefore, negative-feedback mechanisms on TH cells may play a role controlling GH
535 secretion until early adulthood and, once GH secretion decreases after this period, the importance
536 of this TH/GHRH/pituitary system declines with aging or can be compensated by multiple
537 redundant mechanisms that exist to control GH secretion (Steyn et al., 2016).

538 In summary, we unraveled a critical and previously unidentified group of catecholaminergic
539 interneurons that are apt to sense changes in circulating GH levels and consequently regulate
540 *Ghrh* expression to auto control the somatotropic axis. Based on these findings, we propose a
541 reevaluation of the short-loop feedbacks that regulate GH secretion to include these TH+/DAT-
542 /DBH- cells as key interneurons that sense circulating GH levels and use GHRH neurons as
543 downstream effectors to regulate the somatotropic axis (Fig. 12).

544

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716 **Figure Legends**

717 **Figure 1.** Catecholaminergic neurons are responsive to GH. **A-F**, Epifluorescence
 718 photomicrographs showing double-labeling immunofluorescence staining of pSTAT5 (green) and
 719 TH-immunoreactivity (TH-ir; red) in C57BL/6 male mice that received an injection of porcine GH (*A-
 720 D*) or PBS (*E-F*). The insets represent higher magnification photomicrographs of the selected area
 721 and the arrowheads indicate double-labeled neurons. Abbreviations: 3V, third ventricle; 4V, fourth
 722 ventricle; ARH, arcuate nucleus; LC, locus coeruleus; PV, periventricular nucleus, PVH,
 723 paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus; VMH, ventromedial nucleus. Scale bars: 100 μ m in
 724 A,B,C,E; 200 μ m in D,F.

725

726 **Figure 2.** Ablation of GH receptor (GHR) in subpopulations of catecholaminergic neurons or in the
 727 entire brain. **A**, Epifluorescence photomicrograph demonstrating the ablation of GHR in DAT-
 728 expressing cells (visualized by the red tdTomato reporter protein). Note that GH-induced pSTAT5
 729 (green) was only found in DAT negative cells. **B-F**, Epifluorescence photomicrographs
 730 demonstrating the ablation of GHR in TH immunoreactive (TH-ir; red) neurons in the DBH GHR KO
 731 (*B*), TH GHR KO (*C-D*) and BRAIN GHR KO (*E-F*) male mice. The insets represent higher
 732 magnification photomicrographs of the selected area or of the hypothalamus (*B*). Abbreviations:
 733 3V, third ventricle; 4V, fourth ventricle; ARH, arcuate nucleus; LC, locus coeruleus; VMH,
 734 ventromedial nucleus. Scale bars: 100 μ m in A,B,C,E; 200 μ m in D,F.

735

736 **Figure 3.** Consequences of GHR ablation in different subpopulations of catecholaminergic neurons
 737 or in the entire brain of male mice. **A-D**, Body weight (*A*), lean body mass (*B*), body fat mass (*C*)
 738 and naso-anal length (*D*) in 20 week-old control and DAT GHR KO mice ($n = 6-9$). **E-H**, Body
 739 weight (*E*), lean body mass (*F*), body fat mass (*G*) and naso-anal length (*H*) in 20 week-old control
 740 and DBH GHR KO mice ($n = 5-8$). **I-L**, Body weight (*I*), lean body mass (*J*), body fat mass (*K*) and
 741 naso-anal length (*L*) in 10 week-old control and TH GHR KO mice ($n = 9-10$). **M-P**, Body weight
 742 (*M*), lean body mass (*N*), body fat mass (*O*) and naso-anal length (*P*) in 42 week-old control and
 743 TH GHR KO mice ($n = 11$). **Q-T**, Body weight (*Q*), lean body mass (*R*), body fat mass (*S*) and
 744 naso-anal length (*T*) in 20 week-old control and BRAIN GHR KO mice ($n = 8-9$). Data were

745 analyzed using two-tailed Student's *t*-test. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, **** $P < 0.0001$ vs.
 746 control group. Mean \pm s.e.m.

747

748 **Figure 4.** Consequences of growth hormone receptor (GHR) ablation in different subpopulations of
 749 catecholaminergic neurons or in the entire brain of male mice. **A-D**, Liver (A), spleen (B), heart (C)
 750 and kidney (D) masses in 20 week-old DAT GHR KO mice ($n = 7-9$). **E-H**, Liver (E), spleen (F),
 751 heart (G) and kidney (H) masses in 20 week-old DBH GHR KO mice ($n = 5-7$). **I-L**, Liver (I), spleen
 752 (J), heart (K) and kidney (L) masses in 42 week-old TH GHR KO mice ($n = 9-10$). **M-P**, Liver (M),
 753 spleen (N), heart (O) and kidney (P) in 20 week-old BRAIN GHR KO mice ($n = 14$). Data were
 754 analyzed using two-tailed Student's *t*-test. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ vs. control group. Mean \pm s.e.m.

755

756 **Figure 5.** Consequences of GHR ablation in different subpopulations of catecholaminergic neurons
 757 or in the entire brain of male mice. **A-D**, Perigonadal adipose tissue (A), gonadal (B), brain (C) and
 758 gastrocnemius muscle (D) masses in 20 week-old DAT GHR KO mice ($n = 7-9$). **E-H**, Perigonadal
 759 adipose tissue (E), gonadal (F), brain (G) and gastrocnemius muscle (H) masses in 20 week-old
 760 DBH GHR KO mice ($n = 5-7$). **I-L**, Perigonadal adipose tissue (I), gonadal (J), brain (K) and
 761 gastrocnemius muscle (L) masses in 42 week-old TH GHR KO mice ($n = 9-10$). **M-P**, Perigonadal
 762 adipose tissue (M), gonadal (N), brain (O) and gastrocnemius muscle (P) in 20 week-old BRAIN
 763 GHR KO mice ($n = 14$). Data were analyzed using two-tailed Student's *t*-test. ** $P < 0.01$ vs.
 764 control group. N.D., not determined. Mean \pm s.e.m.

765

766 **Figure 6.** Consequences of GHR ablation in different subpopulations of catecholaminergic neurons
 767 or in the entire brain of female mice. **A-C**, Body weight (A), lean body mass (B) and body fat mass
 768 (C) in 10 week-old control and DAT GHR KO females ($n = 10-13$). **D-F**, Body weight (D), lean body
 769 mass (E) and body fat mass (F) in 10 week-old control and DBH GHR KO mice female ($n = 10$). **G-**
 770 **I**, Body weight (G), lean body mass (H) and body fat mass (I) in 10 week-old control and TH GHR
 771 KO mice female ($n = 8-10$). **J-L**, Body weight (J), lean body mass (K) and body fat mass (L) in 10
 772 week-old control and BRAIN GHR KO mice female ($n = 11-14$). Data were analyzed using two-tailed
 773 Student's *t*-test. ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control group. Mean \pm s.e.m.

774

775 **Figure 7.** Pulsatile pattern of GH secretion. **A-C**, Representative examples of the pulsatile pattern
776 of GH secretion in 8 week-old control (A), TH GHR KO (B) and BRAIN GHR KO (C) male mice.

777 Since the y-axis scale has been standardized in all representative cases shown, the insets

778 demonstrate the pulsatile pattern of GH secretion in the control group on a reduced y-axis. **D-F**,

779 Representative examples of the pulsatile pattern of GH secretion in 18 week-old control (D), TH

780 GHR KO (E) and BRAIN GHR KO (F) male mice. The pulsatile pattern of GH secretion was

781 determined by 36 serial blood collections in each mouse at 10-minute intervals during the first 6

782 hours of the light phase.

783

784 **Figure 8.** Loss of GH negative feedback in TH cells or the entire brain raises GH secretion via

785 increased pulse amplitude. **A-C**, Mean GH levels (A), pulse frequency (B) and pulse amplitude (C)

786 in 8 week-old control ($n = 5$), TH GHR KO ($n = 6$) and BRAIN GHR KO ($n = 4$) male mice. **D-F**,

787 Mean GH levels (D), pulse frequency (E) and pulse amplitude (F) in 18 week-old control ($n = 8$),

788 TH GHR KO ($n = 6$) and BRAIN GHR KO ($n = 5$) male mice. The pulsatile pattern of GH secretion

789 was determined by 36 serial blood collections in each mouse at 10-minute intervals during the first

790 6 hours of the light phase. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Bonferroni's multiple

791 comparisons test. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. Mean \pm s.e.m.

792

793 **Figure 9.** Partial co-localization between DAT and TH-immunoreactivity (TH-ir) in the

794 hypothalamus. **A-D**, Epifluorescence photomicrographs showing DAT-expressing cells (visualized

795 by the red tdTomato reporter protein) and TH-ir (green) in male mice. **E**, TH immunoreactive cells

796 (red) are still responsive to GH (pSTAT5; green) in DAT GHR KO male mice. **F**, Virtually no DAT-

797 expressing cells (visualized by the red tdTomato reporter protein) exhibited GH-induced pSTAT5

798 (green) in DAT GHR KO male mice. The insets represent higher magnification photomicrographs

799 of the selected area and the arrows indicate double-labeled neurons. Abbreviations: 3V, third

800 ventricle; ARH, arcuate nucleus; PV, periventricular nucleus, PVH, paraventricular nucleus of the

801 hypothalamus; SNpc, substantia nigra pars compacta. Scale bar = 100 μ m.

802

803 **Figure 10.** GHR ablation in TH cells leads to increased hypothalamic expression of *Ghrh* mRNA.
 804 **A-C,** Gene expression analysis in the whole hypothalamus of 8 week-old control ($n = 5$), TH GHR
 805 KO ($n = 6$) or BRAIN GHR KO ($n = 4$) male mice. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and
 806 Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, **** $P < 0.0001$. Mean \pm s.e.m. **D-E,**
 807 Triple immunofluorescence staining to identify whether SST neurons (visualized by the red
 808 tdTomato reporter protein) express TH-ir (blue) and are responsive to GH (pSTAT5; green) in male
 809 mice. Abbreviations: 3V, third ventricle; ARH, arcuate nucleus; PV, periventricular nucleus. Scale
 810 bar = 50 μ m.

811

812 **Figure 11.** A very small percentage of GHRH cells are responsive to GH and express TH. **A,**
 813 Representative darkfield digital image showing the distribution of *Ghrh* mRNA in the arcuate
 814 nucleus (ARH) by *in situ* hybridization. **B,** Brightfield digital image showing the distribution of
 815 GHRH-eGFP positive cells in the ARH. **C,** Higher magnification of B showing colocalization
 816 (arrows) of *Ghrh* mRNA (silver grains) and GHRH reporter gene (GFP immunoreactive neurons in
 817 brown). **D-G,** Triple immunofluorescence staining to identify whether GHRH neurons (visualized by
 818 the green fluorescent protein) express TH-ir (red) and are responsive to GH (pSTAT5; black
 819 nuclear staining). The arrows indicate triple-labeled neurons. Abbreviations: 3V, third ventricle;
 820 DMH, dorsomedial nucleus of the hypothalamus; VMH, ventromedial nucleus of the hypothalamus.
 821 Scale bars: 100 μ m in A-B; 50 μ m in C; 30 μ m in D-G.

822

823 **Figure 12.** Scheme summarizing the major findings of the present study regarding the short
 824 feedback loops that regulate GH secretion. In the current model, it is believed that GH feeds back
 825 to SST and GHRH positive neurons which in turn exert a regulatory effect on pituitary GH
 826 secretion. In the proposed model, the dashed lines indicate the novel findings of the present study.
 827 We provide additional evidence that only few GHRH neurons are directly responsive to GH; thus,
 828 GHR was removed from GHRH neurons. However, GH action on TH+/DAT-/DBH- neurons is
 829 required to regulate GHRH expression and consequently GH secretion via negative feedback.
 830 Therefore, GHRH neurons are downstream these TH+/DAT-/DBH- neurons. Since ablation of GHR
 831 in the entire brain produces additional changes in GHRH expression, there is an unknown neuronal

832 population that is responsive to GH and indirectly regulates GHRH expression. GHR expression in
833 DAT+ or DBH+ positive cells is dispensable for the regulation of the somatotrophic axis.
834 Abbreviations: DAT, dopamine transporter; DBH, dopamine beta-hydroxylase; GHRH, growth
835 hormone-releasing hormone; ME, median eminence; SST, somatostatin; TH, tyrosine hydroxylase.

20 week-old males

20 week-old males

42 week-old males

20 week-old males

20 week-old males

20 week-old males

42 week-old males

20 week-old males

A 8 weeks of age

B

C

D 18 weeks of age

E

F

